

The illumination - vertical circle as light source with absorption

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We turn to the illumination (in the visual area).

We view a circular disk and a point p with the distance r . The circular disk shall be the light source Q with the luminous intensity I . the whole room is vacuum, see figure.

R is the radius of the circular disk.

$w = \frac{I}{(2) \cdot \pi \cdot R^2}$ is the surface luminous intensity density

(2) if both sides are radiating.

We find the illumination:

$$\vec{E} = \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{wR}{(r^2 + \bar{x}^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \left[\begin{pmatrix} r \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \bar{x} \cos \alpha \\ \bar{x} \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix} \right] d\alpha d\bar{x} \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{x} \in [0, R]$$

R is the root of Gram determinant of the interior integral Now it is:

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \begin{pmatrix} r \\ -\bar{x} \cos \alpha \\ -\bar{x} \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix} d\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} 2\pi r \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\Rightarrow \vec{E} = 2\pi w R r \cdot \int_0^R \frac{1}{(r^2 + \bar{x}^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} d\bar{x} \quad (3)$$

integration with Gröbner [1] section 231 p.39 Nr.20b):

$$\vec{E} = 2\pi w R r \cdot \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \cdot \frac{\bar{x}}{\sqrt{r^2 + \bar{x}^2}} \right]_0^R \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

control with differentiation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\bar{x}} \left(\frac{\bar{x}}{\sqrt{r^2 + \bar{x}^2}} \right) &= \frac{\sqrt{r^2 + \bar{x}^2} - \bar{x} \cdot \frac{\bar{x}}{\sqrt{r^2 + \bar{x}^2}}}{r^2 + \bar{x}^2} \\ &= \frac{\frac{r^2 + \bar{x}^2 - \bar{x}^2}{\sqrt{r^2 + \bar{x}^2}}}{(r^2 + \bar{x}^2)} = \frac{r^2}{(r^2 + \bar{x}^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \end{aligned}$$

With (4) follows:

$$\vec{E} = \frac{2\pi w R^2}{r \sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

To absolute value we obtain:

$$|\vec{E}| = \frac{2\pi w}{r} \cdot \frac{R^2}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} \quad (6)$$

special cases:

1) $R \ll r$

$$\vec{E} \approx 2\pi w \frac{R^2}{r^2} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

or

$$|\vec{E}| \approx 2\pi w \frac{R^2}{r^2} \quad (8)$$

$$2) \quad r \ll R \quad r > 0$$

$$\vec{E} \approx \frac{2\pi w R}{r} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

or

$$|\vec{E}| \approx \frac{2\pi w R}{r} \quad (10)$$

Now we look at the same situation with a medium in the whole room with the absorption coefficient m . The density of the medium is constant thus m is constant. Then we add the factor e^{-ms} with the distance s that the light has covered.

Thus with (1):

$$\vec{E} = \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{w R e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+\bar{x}^2}}}{(r^2 + \bar{x}^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \left[\begin{pmatrix} r \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \bar{x} \cos \alpha \\ \bar{x} \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix} \right] d\alpha d\bar{x} \quad (11)$$

R is the root of the Gram determinant of the interior integral again, see equation (1). If we take the interior integration as in (2) we get:

$$\vec{E} = 2\pi w R r \cdot \int_0^R \frac{e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+\bar{x}^2}}}{(r^2 + \bar{x}^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} d\bar{x} \quad (12)$$

A representation without integrals is unknown.

We calculate an example with $R=1$ metre and the luminous intensity 1 candela. Only one side is radiating. The absorption coefficient m is (pure air, wavelength = 435 nanometres) $0.00003 \text{ metre}^{-1}$. The illumination is noticed in lux. We get the following table:

r [metre]	$E_x = \vec{E} $	approximation $E_x = \vec{E} $
1	1.4142	2.0000
2	0.4440	0.5000
3	0.2108	0.2222
4	0.1213	0.1250
5	0.0784	0.0800
6	0.0548	0.0555
7	0.0404	0.0408
8	0.0310	0.0313
9	0.0245	0.0247
10	0.0200	0.0200

References

- [1] Wolfgang Gröbner und Nikolaus Hofreiter "Integraltafel Erster Teil" 5.edition 1975 Springer Verlag Vienna
- [2] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001